

IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE RULES IN SPEECH ACTIVITY IN PRIMARY EDUCATION.

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Abstract: In this article, the importance of language rules in speech activity in primary education mother tongue classes and reading literacy classes is analyzed scientifically and theoretically.

Key words: Science, linguistic ability, speaking, A. M. Shakhnarovich, definition, functional system, native language system, reflection of its elements, generalization, result, linguistic units, psychological reality, recognition, etc.

Introduction: Currently, the nature of the language phenomenon cannot be determined without taking into account how this unit is expressed in the individual language system of the native speaker. Deviations from the norm in the analysis of the speech of adults and children and their fixation in the mind of the speaker and the listener circumstances play a special role. They clearly indicate the truth of the norm itself as a set of rules.

Literature review: The functioning of the rules governing human speech activity should also be discussed. Speaking about the linguistic ability of a person, A. M. Shakhnarovich describes it as follows: "It is a certain functional system, which is the result of reflecting (and generalizing) the elements of the native language system and works according to certain rules. Recognition of the psychological reality of language units, in our opinion, implies recognition of psychological reality.

The rules of their selection and construction in the process of speech activity. However, understanding the rule requires a very important explanation. Several times we had to deal with a narrow (traditionally called school) interpretation of the concept of "rule".

It is with the understanding of the rule that it becomes possible to contrast the rule and analogy and to discuss the question of what guides a person in speech activity - this or that. Based on a different, broader interpretation of the concept of a rule, which is understood as a guide for speech actions in the process of speech formation, it can be argued that it is the establishment of similarities, the determination of something similar by each individual. In the content and form of the main linguistic units lies the way of understanding the rules that exist in the language. If a person did not have this ability, it would not be possible to understand the language (not the first or second), as well as the transmission of the language from generation to generation. If we understand the interconnected patterns through the rules of certain linguistic units, we must admit that it is almost impossible to count their number (rules). Thus, for example, among the rules that determine the choice of a noun when creating a statement, it is necessary to list all the meanings given by explanatory words. The factors that indicate the field of their reference and the rules that determine the morphological form of the noun are mandatory. It takes into account all the semantic and structural functions of the grammars that make up the morphological categories specific to the noun - it ensures the correct choice of the form. However, knowledge of linguistic patterns (of course, it is possible to choose a language unit on the basis of purely practical) and switch from one unit. This also applies to its paradigmatic and syntagmatic aspects. In descriptive grammars, these patterns are presented in inflectional or word-forming paradigms, syntactic models, or otherwise, usually in a more economical form. In the process of speech activity, a person faced with the task of forming a word formed from another word form or from a forming word performs the necessary speech operations using the knowledge of these patterns, for example, movement.

From the noun form of the noun, replace A with U, to the form of the accusative case that it needs (kitab a - kitab). When one word form is derived from another (initial), the support cannot be only a so-called initial word. The form of the nominative unit of the noun, but any other, first of all, is found in the immediate context 1. Of course, such a person does not clearly formulate the rules of transition from one form to another; but nevertheless, they are

undoubtedly the reality of the human linguistic mind. In every movement o There is no need to talk about the possibility of consciously applying the learned rules, if most of the rules are never described in the publications aimed at the native speaker, precisely because he already speaks. From this moment, we can talk about the beginning of the stage of productivity in relation to the morphological component of the system. The child is able to build word forms independently, relying on the rules he has determined to pass from one form to another. These initial rules are obtained based on processing the speech input received by it; they are both similar and unlike the rules that govern adult language speakers when they form similar forms at the same time. Since the rules that apply to a developing child's grammar are the result of analogy established by the child, these rules reflect what is generally an invariant, prototypical way of morphological marking. Any linguistic unit is understood by the child in two ways. It is mastered as a unit of essence, signifier and signifier, and since the basis of any speech act is the desire to express this or that content, to provide information, the content side of language units is of primary importance.

Above, in addition to the rules for creating units related to the expression plan of language units and categories, there are also rules for choosing a language unit: lexeme, morphological form, as well as syntactic schemes related to necessity. It is noted that the generational speech process for building phrases, sentences (simple and complex) has long required grammar, and the rules for choosing the morphological form necessary to convey the necessary morphological meaning do not cause special difficulties for the child to learn. Russian as mother tongue. At the same time, it turns out that this very operation, which is necessary to create any word, is always difficult for a foreign speaker. Let's look at one example from the published area of verb type selection. Below are examples of Russian speech by Azerbaijanis, but similar mistakes are also found among speakers of other languages that do not have the verb aspect category.

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